

Machine learning framework to predict instantaneous heat release rate of polymer nanocomposites in cone calorimetry

Junchen Xiao^{a,b}, Jose Hobson^a, Maciej Haranczyk^{a*}, De-Yi Wang^{a*}

^a IMDEA Materials Institute, C/Eric Kandel, 2, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain.

^b Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, E.T.S. de Ingenieros de Caminos, 28040 Madrid, Spain.

*Emails: maciej.haranczyk@imdea.org , deyi.wang@imdea.org

Abstract

A comprehensive understanding of fire behavior in a specific combustion scene is essential concerning the fire safety of materials. Cone Calorimetry (CCT), a worldwide benchmark lab-testing method in this field, reveals the heat release rate (HRR) over time, indicating the size and scale of the fire. On account of the Process-Structure-Property-Performance (PSPP) relationships, machine learning models have provided a shortcut to predict the HRR of a given composition of polymer composites before experimental testing. Here, we developed a machine learning framework using chained Random Forest Classifiers (RFC) to predict the HRR over time of polymer composites, which are loaded with Metal Hydroxide (MH) as flame retardant. Nine models were built with high R^2 over 0.83 and low mean absolute errors (MAE). Comparison between predicted and real HRR curves of additional validation samples show good overlapping in 4 samples. Typical characteristics like time to ignition, peak HRR and total heat release rate obtained from the predicted and measured curves were basically identical.

Keywords: *Data-driven prediction; Heat release rate; Flame retardancy; Polymer composites; Cone calorimetry;*

1. Introduction

In natural science, trial-and-error is an essential concept to reach empirical rules and guide new designs. Especially when researchers aim to achieve better performance of materials or meet new requirements, numerous formulations and various types of materials have been engaged. In recent years, the research paradigms have begun to change due to the powerful computational tools. A. Agrawal and A. Choudhary concluded the ‘four paradigms of science’ in 2016, in which the fourth phase of material research came out with (big) data-driven science. [1] There is no doubt that material informatics is attracting more and more interest. Many examples using this new-generation tool have sprung up in predicting the performance-related properties of materials.

In material science, research on materials under fire conditions has been motivated by the need for casualties and property losses. The heat release rate (HRR) from ignited pieces in a combustion scene is considered one of the most critical parameters. [2] The interactions between fire and the surrounding environment depend on the value of the HRR. [3] At the laboratory level, HRR is commonly measured using a calorimeter under conditions that may be expected in an actual fire. [4] The most significant bench-scale calorimeter is the Cone Calorimeter, named after its truncated cone-shape heater, which is now widely used by leading research groups in the fire safety field. [5]

The cone calorimeter test (CCT) adopted by the International Organization of Standardization (ISO 5660-1) collects essential characteristics like the heat release rate per unit (HRR) while burning well-prepared samples. The calculation of HRR is based on oxygen consumption and illustrated against the time as the HRR curve. [6] It provides considerable insight into the physical-chemical reactions, transfer of heat and mass, and occurrence of possible burning instabilities during combustion [7]. This makes the HRR curve very sensitive to the experimental environment and specimen conditions. [8] The shape, fluctuation and peak positions of curves have certain connections to the existence of different flame retardant compositions.

Many researchers have worked on mathematical modeling of combustion to enable concise calculation of desired physical quantities. From the combustion dynamics of fuel fire [9] to the two-

step decomposition of binary blends [10], estimation of pyrolysis properties based on mathematical models [11] to natural smoke filling time in an atrium with floor fire [12], various models and correlations were applied. Calculation of HRR is certainly an indispensable attempt from intumescent polymer composites fire in 1996 [13] to dual-fuel fire in 2017 [14]. HRR has been investigated in different combustion scenes; bench-scale CCT is one of them. [2,15] However, on account of the complexity of FR mechanisms, diversity of involved reactants and variability of combustion circumstances, the accurate mathematical calculation still needs to be improved.

Fig. 1 Four research paradigms and PSPP relationships in material science

In 1997, G. B. Olson discussed the three-link chain model connecting science and engineering in material research: an ascensive scientific link between Processing-Structure-Properties-Performance (PSPP) in **Fig. 1**. [16] This deductive flow describes the progressive cause-and-effect relationship from ingredients to produced samples. A proper database containing abundant information about processing and structure enables the researchers to build predictive models. Verified Machine Learning (ML) models can shorten the time consumed and decrease the cost of facility and materials to support experiments or simulations. Many groups have employed ML algorithms to make predictions on different physical and chemical properties. [17,18] Most of these works focus on the prediction of

individual properties, real-time HRR prediction has more advantages in acquiring CCT characteristics, revealing burning conditions and understanding FR progress.

In this work, we have developed a machine learning framework to predict the HRR curve, simulating the whole measurement in CCT. The involved training dataset was revealed from the collection of publications and experiments on polymer nanocomposites using metal hydroxide as the primary flame retardant additive. The whole framework was built with a supervised ML algorithm, Random Forest. [19,20] It is an ensemble learning method combining multiple decision trees, which gives the advantage of feature importance analysis. The prediction of the HRR curve is based on simplifying the continuous curve to key anchor points and re-connecting the discrete points. Our approach involved 9 RF models, predicting these anchor points and contributing to re-plot the predicted HRR over time.

2. Methodology

2.1. Simplification of HRR curve

Understanding the HRR in a cone is indispensable for accurate prediction of HRR development with a limited dataset. Calculation of HRR based on oxygen consumption is in accordance with Thornton's rule: the energy released by fire is nearly proportional to the corresponding oxygen consumed as equation (1), in which \dot{q} is the heat released, \dot{m}_{O_2} means the oxygen in incoming air and output gases, and E is the proportionality coefficient. Most fuels generate 13.1 kJ of heat on average per gram of oxygen, and this formula is used as the theoretical basis of the oxygen consumption calorimeter. [21]

$$\dot{q} = E \cdot (\dot{m}_{O_2}^{in} - \dot{m}_{O_2}^{out}) = 13.1 \Delta \dot{m}_{O_2} \quad (1)$$

The change of HRR over time represents not only the combustion stages of samples in a given circumstance but also reveals the influence of possible interior processes occurring in a burning scene. The compositions, thermal properties and sample sizes significantly impact the shape of HRR curve. Still, in general, there are three fundamental phases distinguishing the fire behaviors as shown in **Fig. 2(a)** [22,23], except for the incipient time before ignition:

Fig. 2 Heat release rate (HRR) curves in CCT. (a): 3 main combustion phases of HRR over time; (b): key anchor points representing significant features of HRR; (c): examples of simplified HRR curves

(i). The initial phase is recognized by the increased composition of flammable small-molecule gas produced by pyrolysis in high ventilation. Local temperature rising leads to the ignition of sufficient fuels and the sample surface. [24] Usually, the parabola (t^2 fire [25]) is used to describe the increasing heat release rate.

(ii). In the second stage, the fire develops. The growing amount of heat released by combustion, in turn, raises the temperature and promotes the flaming. HRR reveals a general trend of fast increase as a joint result of growing fire density and continuing ventilation. [26] Neat polymers generally show a single peak of HRR in this phase. However, taking the possible flame-retardant (FR) effects into consideration, HRR changes may be greatly influenced: strong fire-hindering effect shall suppress its growth and make HRR curves low and prolonged in time; FR additives that are not efficient enough can temporally restrain HRR growth but the second peak is still possible.

(iii). The last stage is the decaying of fire density with HRR decrease, which is basically caused by the lack of fuel. In general, the exponential decaying function is applied to describe the HRR decrease with the reduction of fuels in this stage. Related equations are shown in (2) to (4), in which H_{rr} is the heat release rate, $\frac{dW}{dt}$ the mass loss of sample, h the equivalent heat capacity of fuels, $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ the conversion of fuels from the sample and k, k_1, k_2 the constant coefficients in fuel-limited burning. [27,28]

$$H_{rr} = h \frac{dW}{dt} \quad (2)$$

$$W'' = k_1 \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_2 \frac{dW}{dt} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dH_{rr}}{dt} = kH_{rr} \quad (4)$$

In light of this, we have conducted the simplification of HRR curves by choosing five key anchor points to make the prediction of HRR possible, as shown in **Fig. 2(b)**. Each point is featured with specific pairs (t, hrr) with units of s and kW/m^2 . In most cases, polymer composites show complex changes in HRR in the second phase due to their FR additives. These transitions indicate different FR effects occurring in CCT, as mentioned above. The critical point of the transition phase is then established to mark different transition trends.

In order to gather data that has high confidence and good operability, the start- and end-points are concluded with HRRs equaling 25 and 50 kW/m^2 separately. The transition point (t_{trans}, hrr_{trans}) either locates in the inflection point or is calculated as the middle point of (t_{devlp}, hrr_{devlp}) and (t_{decay}, hrr_{decay}) . The assessment of ML frameworks is schematically illustrated in **Fig. 3**. According to the shape of transition lines, the to-be-predicted HRR curves can be roughly divided into three different types of peak-, stair- and valley-transition shown in **Fig. 4(b)**. Detailed explanations and definitions of the anchor points are included in **Table 1**. To obtain the coordinate values of these key points, we used the convenient tool Digitalizer in OriginLab, in which the graphs of measured HRR curves were imported and analyzed in pixels.

2.2. Data collection and model assessment

Instead of predicting the entire curve, properties from five key points are to be predicted as the target features. The Dataset used for modeling was revealed from past publications and experimental records. We choose to employ the Random Forest Classifier (RFC) in our work for several reasons. As a supervised ensemble method, RFC concludes the final classification according to the majority voting of results from the randomly grown decision trees (DT) that form the forest in **Fig. 3(a)**. With the if-then-else decision rules, a sample imported into a DT will be determined node by node logistically to

reach its “terminal”, making the model simple to understand and interpret. Moreover, the input features reflecting the influence factors in polymer composites’ combustion are ranked by corresponding importance derived from the Gini index. Considering the physical sense in reality, we can not only achieve high model performance by selecting proper features but also gain deeper insight into the underlying processes in the combustion scene of polymer nanocomposites. [29]

Fig. 3 Structure of Random Forest Algorithm (a) and the chained machine learning framework in this work (b).

We use classifier instead of regressor to make predictions of the above-mentioned properties. The main reason lies in the fact that HRR values contain certain errors. As described in section 2.2, HRR is not directly measurable. The curves concluded from cone tests show clear distinctions in different measurements. [30] These uncertainties come from fuel composition, environmental conditions and instrument accuracy [31], and vary with different flame sizes from 5% to 20% [32,33]. Empirically, we take the assumption of a 10% error in the cone test. In MH-loaded composites, the endothermic reactions of hydroxide decomposition also produce considerable errors to some degree. [34] In

consequence, predicting the categorical levels instead of numerical values enables accuracy improvement while maintaining significant information on HRR development.

Table 1

Five key anchor points to simplify measured HRR curves

Key anchor point	Format	Interpretation
Ignition	$(t_{ignit}, 25)$	Ignition point, sample begins to burning when measured HRR reaches 25kW/m ² .
Developing	(t_{devlp}, hrr_{devlp})	Developing points, previous parabolic burning slows down, new combustion phase dominated by HRR or ventilation begins.
Transition	(t_{trans}, hrr_{trans})	Transition point, HRR changes also depending on the FR effect of composites composition.
Decaying	(t_{decay}, hrr_{decay})	Decaying point, HRR starts to decrease due to fuel limitation.
Afterglow	$(t_{after}, 50)$	Afterglow point, flame faints till HRR reaches 50kW/m ² .

In this ML framework, 9 different models based on RFC were built. The input dataset was randomly split into training and test sets, corresponding to 85% and 15%, respectively. The overall structure of models is illustrated in **Fig. 3(b)**. Model #x was designed to predict the target property listed on the right end. The chained models, i.e., model #2 took not only the collected dataset but also the predictive results of model #1 (t_{ignit}) as input. The green lines indicate this extra input for models #2 to #5 and #7 to #8.

In the collected dataset, various features are divided into 5 groups, representing the potential, specific sources that influence HRR development. They are listed below:

- 1) Polymer Matrix: Features related to neat polymer are bound to this group, consisting of the density, thermal conductivity, CCT characteristics of neat polymer and any other possible physical and chemical properties.
- 2) Metal Hydroxide: The thermal decomposition properties, particle size and loading amount are the main features in this group. It is considered to be an individual group due to its main flame-retardant effect in polymer composites that are different from other synergists.
- 3) Synergist: Other FR additives besides MH. They can be any kind of compounds, chemicals or inorganic fillers that provide additional synergistic functions between metal hydroxides and polymer matrix. The main features in this group include their elemental composition and mass fraction.
- 4) Experimental Parameter: This group focuses on the parameters in preparation and measurements of samples that possibly have an impact on the composites' HRR, e.g., the temperatures used to produce samples, their shape and size, as well as heat flux in CCT.
- 5) Composites Property: Properties of the nanocomposites, measured with other methods like TGA and densimeter. Composites' properties in early stages also act as input in predicting these properties in later stages, as shown in **Fig. 3(b)**. These features can improve the predictive accuracy to some extent.

The target properties predicted with classifiers are *curve_type*, and 8 *hrr* and *t* coordinates listed in **Table 1** are converted from numbers to categories. Due to the large range between values of *t_ignit* to that of *t_after* (vary from 10 to 2000 s), time-referring features were logarithmically transformed (base=10) and then categorized. By comparison, *hrr* -properties were firstly divided by the corresponding values of neat polymer before categorizing into levels.

2.3. Validation samples

Polymer composite samples were prepared to validate the accuracy of the ML framework. All samples were prepared with MH as the main flame retardant, with additional synergists added to improve the FR effects. Their compositions are listed in **Table 2**. Two commercial products of Ethylene-vinyl

acetate (both with 28 wt.-% vinyl acetate content) were used, bought from DuPont Company and Hanwha Company, respectively. Inorganic filler magnesium di-hydroxide (MDH) and aluminum tri-hydroxide (ATH) both come from Sigma-Aldrich company in analytical standards. POH-C12 was a self-synthesized organic additive containing phosphorus of about 10 wt.-%. MOF-1 was obtained from the company MOF Technologies (Fe-BTC with 262.96 g/mol molecular weight).

Table 2

Polymer composites for model validation

Sample label	Polymer matrix	FR additives (in wt.-%)	comments
EVA-1	EVA #0	53 MDH + 2 POH-C12	High MH loading sample
EVA-2	EVA #1	25 MDH	EVA #1 has higher pHRR (up to 1500kW/m ²) than EVA #0
EP-3	Epoxy C	17 MDH	Epoxy C with 21wt.-% DDM as curing agent
EP-4	Epoxy C	20 ATH + 1 MOF-1	ATH combined with MOF-1
EP-5	Epoxy C	20 ATH + 2 MOF-1	Ibid.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Dataset representation

The collected dataset consists of 130 records, which were used to train and test 9 RFC models. Based on the transition phase, HRR curves are divided into valley-, stair- and peak-transition as shown in **Fig. 4(b)**. Simplification of HRR still retained such trends. In the whole dataset, samples with valley-shaped HRR curve have the largest amount of 80. The effective loading amount of MH in polymer composites contributes to lowering the HRR in the transition phase, which is the majority of records in the dataset. The occurrence of the second peak of HRR is attributed to an unsteady physical barrier formed by metal oxides that is not able to overcome the propagation of fire. Stair-transition indicates a dynamic balance between the development and suppression of combustion. In the dataset, the amounts of samples with stair- and peak-transitions are 28 and 22, respectively.

Fig. 4 Types of HRR curves in collected dataset: (a) amount distribution; (b) examples of 3 types

Fig. 5 is the comparison between simplifications and real measurements of HRR of 5 experimental samples for validation. Blue curves stand for the measured HRR and yellow for simplified curves. The simplifications have excellent consistency with measured ones. Although there are fluctuations ignored, evident peaks and HRR transitions over time are well reserved. The measurement of HRR based on oxygen consumption is highly susceptible to facility adjustment, surrounding conditions and researcher operations. There are no two identical combustion processes in the testing. As a result, repeated experiments must be conducted on samples in the same batch to avoid abnormal results. The simplification method here can significantly reduce the difficulty in modeling in a way that loses as little information as possible, assuming that there are no critical, objective influences caused by the environment. More attention is then paid to the developing trends of HRR of the combustion processes in the cone calorimeter test.

3.2 Statistical machine learning models

Three commonly used statistical model indices (R², MAE and RMSE) are calculated for all 9 models in **Table 3**. In test set, predicting *curve_type* has the highest R² of 0.89. Other models predicting the *t* and *hrr* coordinates also exhibit high R² varied between 0.83 to 0.87. Compared to the multi-class ranges of all target features, their mean errors are very small. MAEs for all models are equal to

approximately 0.2. Although the RMSE is slightly higher in models aimed to predict *hrr* and later anchor points (trans-, decay- and after-point), it still remains at a low level below 1.

Fig. 5 Comparing the simplifications and measurements of polymer composites.

Besides the above indices, the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) metric using the micro-averaged one-vs-rest technique is calculated and plotted in this multi-category classification. In simple terms, the ratio of correct predictions to false ones is treated as predictive performance. The closer the whole ROC curve is to the top left, the higher the predictive accuracy reaches. Area under the curve (AUC) percentages as a rough judgment of the accuracy of all 9 models are above 90%, except for *hrr_devlp* with 89.76%, indicating effective classification results of our ML models. (See **Fig. S1** ROC plots in **support information**)

Seen from the evaluation indices shown above, the predictive accuracy of all 9 target features is relatively high. The ML framework fits our MH-loaded polymer composites very well. On one side, the FR mechanisms of such long-term applied additives are almost transparent, which makes it easier to extract proper features purposefully; on the other side, conversion of the numeric regression to categorical classification has brought an advantage in prediction.

Table 3

Model indices in training and test sets, including categories of all target features.

Target feature	Categories	R2		MAE		RMSE	
		training set	test set	training set	test set	training set	test set
curve_type	0 - 2	0.99	0.89	0.01	0.17	0.07	0.53
t_ignit	1 - 12	1.0	0.86	0	0.23	0	0.66
t_devlp	3 - 13	1.0	0.84	0	0.19	0	0.5
t_trans	7 - 16	1.0	0.85	0	0.24	0	0.68
t_decay	7 - 19	1.0	0.83	0	0.26	0	0.65
t_after	11 - 19	1.0	0.84	0	0.27	0	0.86
hrr_devlp	1 - 7	1.0	0.83	0	0.2	0	0.49
hrr_trans	1 - 8	0.98	0.83	0.02	0.28	0.14	0.82
hrr_decay	1 - 9	1.0	0.87	0	0.23	0	0.81

3.3 Feature importance analysis

In our ML framework, selected features are divided into five groups concerning all aspects of sample preparation and CCT parameters. The feature groups are ranked by their Gini importance in **Fig. 6** for all models. The sum of the importance is 1 for all models. Higher importance means this feature group is more significant in deciding the target property. In feature selection, considering the feature importance is an essential part of the strategy.

The purple bar representing the feature group “polymer matrix” takes either first or second place in all 9 models. Especially in predicting *curve_type*, importance of 0.58 makes the properties of neat polymer dominant. Loading of MH affects mostly the *hrr_devlp* with 0.32 importance. In other models, the importance of “metal hydroxide” is also comparable to the feature group “synergist”. Feature group “composites property” ranks first in models of *t_decay*, *hrr_trans* and *hrr_decay*, indicating their

strong influence on the development of HRR over time. The influences of “experimental parameters” are lower than the above feature groups due to the fact that only up to 3 features are covered in this group. Although the CCT setup has a strong and complex influence, researchers intend to use similar parameters to ensure the reproducibility of experimental results [35]. In **Fig. S2 of supporting information** are detailed distributions of the feature importance of individual features.

Fig. 6 Importance of all features selected to build the random forest models predicting Lv-TTI (a), D-pHRR (b), Lv-THR (c) and Lv-FRI (d); Coloured legends illustrate the parent groups of each feature.

Fig. 6 gives an overview of the influence of feature groups, but the importance of single features behaves differently. Although the “polymer matrix” takes the first place in predicting t_{ignit} and t_{devlp} , the most important features are still the mass fraction of MH and residue mass of composites after TGA. It is not surprising that the main and most important FR mechanism is the formation of the physical barrier of metal oxide in the combustion process. The features related to mass fraction and burning residue decide the quantity and quality of this protective layer. Furthermore, the importance

of the synergist's amount and its oxygen content follows closely to MH loading since the synergist is intended to assist or enhance the layer structure.

3.4 HRR curve comparison of validation samples

The ML framework is designed to predict the development of HRR in the whole CCT process. Validation samples based on different polymers and loading of MH were prepared and tested. In **Fig. 7**, blue lines represent the measured HRR curves of all 5 samples, whereas the red ones are the predicted HRR curves re-drawn through the five key anchor points.

In general, predicted HRR curves are in high agreement with measurements of all samples, especially for EVA-1 and EP-4. Through the predictions of developing HRR, relative characteristics like time to ignition, peak HRR, time to peak HRR and total heat release from the CCT can be obtained as measured in reality. The trends of how HRR changes over time due to the addition of flame retardants and preparation of polymer composites are accurately maintained. The EVA-1 sample with valley-transition has the highest MH loading of 53 wt.-%, which makes it extremely effective in lowering the heat release. The predicted HRR looks almost overlapped with the measured HRR. The same high accuracy in predicting is observed in the EP-4 sample containing 20 wt.-% ATH and 1 wt.-% of MOF. Through the development of HRR curves, the addition of MOF enhances the effect of flame retardancy, leading to the continuous decrease of HRR in the transition phase. This can be found from the slightly denser and stronger residues left from samples after CCT in **Fig. S3 of supporting information**, which is also observed in other publications using MOF as FR additives [36].

However, there are still comparable errors. The prediction of HRR curves is realized by segmentation and reassembling combustion phases, which are affected by complex physical and chemical compositions in the burning inside CCT. Theoretically, the precursory simplification of HRR curves assumes that the HRR shall have evident change (i.e., achieving local maximum or minimum, or plateau value with enough long time) in entering next combustion phases. But some measurements do not always show clear anchor points in CCT results, leading to inaccuracy in collecting data for training the models. Another error in simplification is the ignorance of small fluctuations of real curves.

The testing curves in physical space are not as smooth as our re-drawn lines. These small but disharmonious changes can be responses of HRR to the sensitive testing conditions or simply measuring errors.

Fig. 7 Comparison between measured and predicted HRR curves for EVA and EP samples

The last disadvantage of this ML framework is the prediction of sharp peaks, which last only for a short time in HRR curves, i.e., the prediction of EVA-2. Such sharp peaks of HRR usually happen in the violent burning of small amounts of fuel or theoretically thermal thin samples like neat polymers with high flammability. On one side, our framework categorized the time characteristics with logarithmic processing, making the model un-sensitive to the change in a small time range. On the other side, suitable FR composites are expected to have low peak HRR and suppressed HRR over time. The data collected from publications and experiments come from the efforts made in this direction, which causes inaccuracy in predicting sharp peaks similarly.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we successfully apply a data-driven approach to predict the heat release rate of polymer composites over combustion time in the cone calorimeter test. The whole framework consists of key-points-simplification, chained-modeling and HRR-curve-recovery. Five key anchor points marking combustion phases are selected to represent the HRR development without losing much information. Models are built with the Random Forest Classifier and R² values varying from 0.83 to 0.89 in test sets indicate high accuracy in predicting all desired target properties. Low errors below 1 level for all categories are also achieved in all models. Feature importance analysis contributes to selecting features and improving predictive performance. Although the ranking of all feature groups shows that the influence factors on HRR still come from all aspects, the latter part of HRR curves is more influenced by features related to MH loading and composites properties, while the features about neat polymer affect transition phase and time to ignition more deeply.

The comparison between predicted and measured HRR curves of validation experiments manifests the high accuracy of our models. Through the predicted HRR curves, researchers can calculate typical CCT characteristics like time to ignition, peak heat release rate, and total heat release without conducting practical measurements, saving costs in time and materials. Besides, this framework is expandable with a further collection of CCT data of polymer composites with advanced flame retardants, promoting the investigation of the heat release rate in complex systems.

Acknowledgements

The authors also acknowledge the financial support provided DIGIBIOFAM Project (TED2021-131409B-I00) funded by Ministerio De Ciencia E Innovación, Spain.

References

- [1] A. Agrawal, A. Choudhary, Perspective: Materials informatics and big data: Realization of the “fourth paradigm” of science in materials science, *APL Mater.* 4 (2016) 53208. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4946894>.
- [2] V. Babrauskas, Heat Release Rates, in: M.J. Hurley, D. Gottuk, J.R. Hall, K. Harada, E. Kuligowski, M. Puchovsky, J. Torero, J.M. Watts, C. Wieczorek (Eds.), *SFPE Handbook of Fire Protection Engineering*, Springer New York, New York, NY, 2016, pp. 799–904.
- [3] Dusso A., Grimaz S., Salzano E., Rapid Estimation of the Heat Release Rate of Combustible Items, *Chemical Engineering Transactions* 53 (2016) 25–30. <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1653005>.
- [4] D.L. Chamberlain, Heat release rate properties of wood-based materials.
- [5] Maluk C, Bisby L, Terrasi G, Krajcovic M, Torero JL (Eds.), *Novel Fire Testing Methodology: Why, how and what now?*, 2012.
- [6] Babrauskas V., Development of the cone calorimeter-A bench-scale heat release rate apparatus based on oxygen consumption, *Fire Mater.* 8 (1984) 81–95. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fam.810080206>.
- [7] T. Zhou, P. Tang, T. Ye, Machine learning based heat release rate indicator of premixed methane/air flame under wide range of equivalence ratio, *Energy* 263 (2023) 126103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.126103>.
- [8] Q. Xu, C. Jin, Y. Jiang, Compare the flammability of two extruded polystyrene foams with micro-scale combustion calorimeter and cone calorimeter tests, *J Therm Anal Calorim* 127 (2017) 2359–2366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-016-5754-6>.
- [9] Candel S., combustion dynamics and control: Progress and Challenges, *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 29 (2002) 1–28. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1540-7489\(02\)80007-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1540-7489(02)80007-4).

- [10] R. Sonnier, A. Viretto, L. Dumazert, B. Gallard, A method to study the two-step decomposition of binary blends in cone calorimeter, *Combustion and Flame* 169 (2016) 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2016.04.016>.
- [11] W.-H. Park, K.-B. Yoon, H.-C. Chang, T.-K. Kim, Estimation of pyrolysis-related properties using repulsive particle swarm optimization, *J Mech Sci Technol* 26 (2012) 2129–2132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12206-012-0529-x>.
- [12] G.-Y. Wu, R.-C. Chen, The Analysis of the Natural Smoke Filling Times in an Atrium, *Journal of Combustion* 2010 (2010) 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2010/687039>.
- [13] Jozef Rychlý, Lyda Rychlá, Modeling of heat release rate-time curves from cone calorimeter for burning of polymers with intumescence additives, *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 54 (1996) 249–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(96\)00050-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(96)00050-X).
- [14] J. Lee, S. Chu, K. Min, M. Kim, H. Jung, H. Kim, Y. Chi, Classification of diesel and gasoline dual-fuel combustion modes by the analysis of heat release rate shapes in a compression ignition engine, *Fuel* 209 (2017) 587–597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2017.07.067>.
- [15] PENG Xiao-qin, LIU Song-lin, LU Guo-jian, Experimental Analysis on Heat Release Rate of Materials, *Journal of Chongqing University (Natural Science Edition)* 28 (2005) 122–125.
- [16] G.B. Olson, Computational Design of Hierarchically Structured Materials, *Science* 277 (1997) 1237–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.277.5330.1237>.
- [17] C.-T. Chen, G.X. Gu, Machine learning for composite materials, *MRS Communications* 9 (2019) 556–566. <https://doi.org/10.1557/mrc.2019.32>.
- [18] J. Wei, X. Chu, X.-Y. Sun, K. Xu, H.-X. Deng, J. Chen, Z. Wei, M. Lei, Machine learning in materials science, *InfoMat* 1 (2019) 338–358. <https://doi.org/10.1002/inf2.12028>.
- [19] F. Legrain, J. Carrete, A. van Roekeghem, G.K.H. Madsen, N. Mingo, Materials Screening for the Discovery of New Half-Heuslers: Machine Learning versus ab Initio Methods, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 122 (2018) 625–632. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b05296>.

- [20] M.Z. Naser, 2021. Observational Analysis of Fire-Induced Spalling of Concrete through Ensemble Machine Learning and Surrogate Modeling. *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* 33, 04020428. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0003525](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0003525).
- [21] M. Werrel, J.H. Deubel, S. Krüger, A. Hofmann, U. Krause, The calculation of the heat release rate by oxygen consumption in a controlled-atmosphere cone calorimeter, *Fire Mater.* 38 (2014) 204–226. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fam.2175>.
- [22] V. Kodur, P. Kumar, M.M. Rafi, Fire hazard in buildings: review, assessment and strategies for improving fire safety, *PRR* 4 (2019) 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PRR-12-2018-0033>.
- [23] M. Chen, Review on Heat Release Reduction of Flexible Polyurethane Foam, *Journal of Xihua University (Natural Science Edition)* 39 (2020) 57–66.
- [24] B. Scharrel, T.R. Hull, Development of fire-retarded materials—Interpretation of cone calorimeter data, *Fire Mater.* 31 (2007) 327–354. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fam.949>.
- [25] National Fire Protection Association, Standard for Smoke Management System in Malls, Atria, and Large Spaces: NFPA 92B, 2005.
- [26] B. Scharrel, K. Kebelemann, Fire Testing for the Development of Flame Retardant Polymeric Materials, in: Y. Hu, X. Wang (Eds.), *Flame Retardant Polymeric Materials*, CRC Press, Boca Raton CRC Press, [2020] | Series: Series in materials science and engineering, 2019, pp. 35–55.
- [27] Richard C. Rothermel, A mathematical model for predicting fire spread in wildland fuels, *Res. Pap. INT-firstfifteenth*, 1972.
- [28] W.-H. Park, K.-B. Yoon, Optimization of pyrolysis properties using TGA and cone calorimeter test, *J. Therm. Sci.* 22 (2013) 168–173. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11630-013-0608-z>.
- [29] C. Zhang, Y. Ma, *Ensemble Machine Learning*, Springer New York, New York, NY, 2012.
- [30] Johan Lindholm, Anders Brink, Mikko Hupa (Eds.), *Cone calorimeter - a tool for measuring heat release rate*, 2008.

- [31] Patrick A. Enright, Charles M. Fleischman, Uncertainty of Heat Release Rate Calculation of the ISO5660-1 Cone Calorimeter Standard Test Method, *Fire Technology* 35 (1999) 153–169. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015416005888>.
- [32] L. Zhao, N.A. Dembsey, Measurement uncertainty analysis for calorimetry apparatuses, *Fire Mater.* 32 (2008) 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fam.947>.
- [33] Clayton Huggett, Estimation of rate of heat release by means of oxygen consumption measurements, *Fire and Materials* 4 (1980) 61–65.
- [34] J. Zhang, X. Wang, F. Zhang, A. Richard Horrocks, Estimation of heat release rate for polymer–filler composites by cone calorimetry, *Polymer Testing* 23 (2004) 225–230. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9418\(03\)00098-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9418(03)00098-9).
- [35] B. ScharTEL, M. Bartholmai, U. Knoll, Some comments on the use of cone calorimeter data, *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 88 (2005) 540–547. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2004.12.016>.
- [36] J. Zhang, Z. Li, L. Zhang, J. García Molleja, D.-Y. Wang, Bimetallic metal-organic frameworks and graphene oxide nano-hybrids for enhanced fire retardant epoxy composites: A novel carbonization mechanism, *Carbon* 153 (2019) 407–416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2019.07.003>.